

A STUDY IN METALLIC-INTERLAYER-REINFORCED

GLASS CLOTH/EPOXY MECHANICAL JOINT

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Summary

The effort of strengthening the mechanically bolted joint efficiency by adding metal interlayer in a composite laminate has been made. The employed metal interlayer was 0.2mm thick, perforated and sandblast-finished SAE 1086 steel sheet. Style 1581 glass cloth and Ciba Geigy LY 556 epoxy resin were molded to form the laminate. The present metal interlayers were colaminated with glass epoxy layers at three different volume fraction levels to form double-lap, single-hole specimens. A data basis was experimentally determined to increase the reliance for the application of steel interlayered reinforcement.

The main objectives of present study are sited in (1) the effect of steel shim content on bearing strength, (2) the minimum values of W/D (width/hole diameter) and e/D (end distance/hole diameter) to reach a full bearing strength, and (3) the influence of adding steel shim on the failure mode.

Introduction

A potential weight saving of 50% of advanced composite structures is generally reduced to 30% by practical constraints. One of the major constraints is encountered in the area of joints. In general, the joint method can be adhesively-bonded or/and mechanically-fastened, and the latter is preferable for the cases where repetitive assembly and disassembly for inspection or maintenance are necessary. Despite that mechanical joints have some advantages, they will suffer strength penalty because of the stress concentration and decrease of load capability caused by decrease of area at the hole. Besides these disadvantages, premature failures occurred in the area of mechanical joints is also a well recognized problem^[1-8].

Since high joint efficiency can not be reached for conventional mechanical joints, various local reinforcing methods, such as metallic- and non-metallic-interlayered reinforcements, have been used to develop acceptable joint strengths^[9-11]. The addition of high strength, high ductile metal shims is a way to alleviate local stress concentration and to enhance the bearing strength of the composite laminates^[11]. But very limited experimental data of using metallic interlayers are available to be the references of joint design.

In the present study, the steel shim (SAE 1086) was colaminated as a interlayered reinforcement to intend to improve the joint efficiency for a glass cloth/epoxy composite laminate. A data basis was experimentally determined to increase the reliance for the application of steel interlayered reinforcement. The main objectives are: (1) to explore the effect of volume fraction of metal shim on bearing strength; (2) to find the minimum values of W/D (width/hole diameter) and e/D (end distance/hole diameter) to reach a full bearing strength; (3) to investigate the influence of adding steel shim on the failure mode.

Experimental Procedure

A series of glass cloth/epoxy laminate panels without and with metal shim were fabricated by press molding method with two steel platens. The cloth was Clark-Schwebel style 1581 glass cloth having a nominal thickness of 0.2032mm. The matrix resin system was Ciba Geigy Araldite LY 558 epoxy with HY 906 hardener and DY 061 accelerator. The cure cycle was 70°C, 4 hours; 110°C, 1 hour; 140°C, 3 hours; and then slowly cooled down to room temperature. The added metal shim was SAE 1086 steel sheet with a thickness of 0.2mm. Before colamination, the steel sheet was perforated and sand-blasted to enhance the bonding between glass cloth/epoxy layer and steel shim. The perforation hole was 1mm diameter with 5 holes/cm² intensity. The final experimental panels indicated in Table I were 3mm thick with zero, one, two and four steel interlayers in the overall 9-layered laminates. The volume fractions of steel shims indicated in Table I were obtained by burning the specimens and removing the matrix resin under the condition of 600°C, 1 hour.

Before conducting bearing test, the basic mechanical properties of steel sheet and glass cloth/epoxy laminate were obtained by means of coupon tension test. The test machine was Instron universal test machine and the cross-head speed was 2mm/min. The strains were measured by strain gages. The coupon configurations are shown in Fig. 1.

The specimen configuration for bearing test is shown in Fig. 2. In this study, the single-bolt double-lap joint was used and the whole test unit

Table I. Stacking Sequence, Density, and Volume Fraction of Steel Shim for Tested Panels

Panel Identification	Stacking Sequence	Density g/cm^3	Volume Fraction of Steel Shim $V_s, \%^{***}$
0M*	$[C_9]_T^{**}$	1.64	0
1M	$[C_4/\bar{M}]_S$	2.08	6.59
2M	$[C/M/C_5/M/C]_T$	2.34	11.91
4M	$[C/M/C/M/\bar{C}]_S$	2.93	22.93

* The number indicates the number of steel shim.

** C: glass cloth/epoxy, the direction of applied load is the same as the warp direction of the cloth.

M: SAE 1086 steel shim.

*** Obtained by burning off the resin under the condition of 600°C , 1 hour.

(a) SAE 1086 steel sheet.

(b) Glass cloth/epoxy laminate.

Figure 1 - Tension coupon configuration.

Figure 2 - Specimen configuration for bearing test.

which included specimen and fixture is shown in Fig. 3. The fastening torque of bolt was 5.66 N-m (50 lb-in) and the bearing strength σ_b was calculated by the following equation:

$$\sigma_b = P_{max}/tD \quad (1)$$

Here, P_{max} is maximum tensile load, t is specimen thickness and D is bolt diameter.

Figure 3 - Bearing test set-up

A series of experiments with different values of e/D and W/D were conducted to study the effects of e/D and W/D ratios on the bearing strength. And the visual inspection was used to check the failure mode.

Test Results

The basic mechanical properties of present glass cloth/epoxy laminate and SAE 1086 steel sheet were obtained by coupon tension tests. Figure 4 shows the stress-strain curves for the glass cloth/epoxy laminate and steel sheet and Table II indicates the basic mechanical properties.

The stress-strain relation for glass cloth/epoxy laminate is linear up to final fracture, Fig. 4, and the ultimate strength and strain is 230 MPa and 1.48%, respectively. While the higher strength and the ductility for steel sheet are found from Fig. 4, the yielding strength is 1045 MPa and

Figure 4 - Stress-strain curves of studied laminate and steel sheet.

Table II. Basic Mechanical Properties of Glass Cloth/Epoxy Laminate and Steel Sheet

Material	Gl/E _p Laminate	SAE 1086 Steel Sheet
Tensile strength, MPa	230	1535
Yielding strength E _y *, MPa	-	1045
Ultimate strain E _{max} , %	1.48	1.82
Yielding strain E _y , %	-	0.59
Elastic modulus, GPa	16.6	189
Poisson's ratio	0.167	0.278

* 0.2% off-set yielding strength.

yielding strain is 0.59%. Note that the elastic modulus of steel sheet is about 10 times higher than the value of glass cloth/epoxy laminate, and the yielding strain of 0.59% of steel sheet is much lower than the fracture strain of 1.48% of glass cloth/epoxy laminate. When laminate which colaminated steel shim takes the bearing load, most part of applied load will be carried by steel shim. Because of high strength, high ductility and low yielding strain of the steel shim, the results of alleviation of stress concentration and enhancement of bearing strength can be expected.

Table III shows the results of bearing strength tests for the specimens with steel shim content of 0, 6.59, 11.91 and 22.93%. The results include the ultimate load, bearing strength, effect of W/D ratio, effect of e/D ratio

and failure mode. The following discussion will base on Table III and concentrate on the influences of adding steel interlayer on the bearing strength e/D and W/D ratios to reach full bearing strength, and failure mode.

Table III. Bearing Test Results

Stacking Sequence	Vol. Fraction of Steel Shim Vs, %	W/D	e/D	Ultimate Load** Kg	Bearing Strength MPa	Failure Mode*
[C ₉] _T	0	3.0	3.15	516	265	T
		3.8	3.15	760	390	B/T
		5.0	3.15	743	382	B/T
		6.0	3.15	759	390	B/T
		7.6	3.15	775	398	B/C
		3.8	2.0	493	302	T
		3.8	4.0	651	383	B/T
		3.8	5.0	658	387	B/T
		3.8	6.0	667	392	B/T
[C ₄ /M̄] _S	6.59	3.0	3.15	796	409	T
		3.8	3.15	986	507	B/T
		5.0	3.15	1009	518	B/T
		6.0	3.15	985	506	B/C
		7.6	3.15	991	509	B/C
		3.8	2.0	741	381	C
		3.8	4.0	978	502	B/T
		3.8	6.0	972	499	B/T
		3.8	8.0	974	500	B/T
[C/M/C ₅ /M/C] _T	11.91	3.0	3.15	931	478	T
		3.8	3.15	1302	668	T
		5.0	3.15	1545	794	B/T (2)
		6.0	3.15	1556	799	B/C (2)
		7.6	3.15	1526	784	B/C
		3.8	2.0	1061	545	B/T (2)
		3.8	4.0	1244	639	B/C (2)
		3.8	5.0	1261	647	B/T
		3.8	6.0	1281	658	B/T
8.0	6.0	1585	814	B		
[C/M/C/M/C] _S	22.93	3.0	3.15	1408	723	T
		3.8	3.15	1770	873	T
		5.0	3.15	2136	1097	B/T
		6.0	3.15	2105	1081	B/C
		7.6	3.15	2098	1078	B/C
		3.8	2.0	1435	737	C
		3.8	4.0	1776	912	B/T
		3.8	5.0	1761	905	B/T
		3.8	6.0	1839	903	B/T
8.0	6.0	2037	1046	B		

* T: Tension failure
B: Bearing failure

- C: Cleavage failure.
- /: Initial failure mode/Final failure mode.
- : Number in circle indicates the number of appearance of indicated failure mode.

*** All data are average values of 5 specimens.

Discussion

The Effect of Steel Shim Content on Bearing Strength

The effect of volume fraction of steel shim (V_s) on bearing strength is plotted in Fig. 5 in which W/D and e/D ratios are fixed parameters for each curve.

Figure 5 - The effect of steel shim content on bearing strength.

An increasing tendency of bearing strength by the increasing value of V_s is shown in Fig. 5, and a pretty linear relationship between bearing strength is existent in spite of the ratios of W/D and e/D in the studied range. When full bearing strength for the specimens with 6.59, 11.91 and 22.93% steel shim is 30.8, 103, 178% higher than those specimens without steel shim, respectively. It is obvious that the addition of steel inter-layer enhances the bearing strength and improves the joint efficiency.

The characters of high strength and high ductility of steel shim provide the high bearing capacity and affect the failure behavior strongly. The yielding and ultimate strengths of SAE 1086 steel sheet are also indicated in Fig. 5. When the steel shim content reaches a certain level, the bearing behavior of specimen is dominated by the steel shim, and the ductile phenomenon is imaginable. Indeed the bearing strength will linearly increase by the increase of V_s value, but the non-linear tendency will occur when V_s is relatively large and the applied load is greater than a certain value. The dash lines in Fig. 6 are the inference described above. Note that the non-linear behavior happens only for cases that bearing strength is greater than the yielding strength of steel sheet.

Despite that the addition of steel shim can improve bearing strength, it will suffer weight penalty. We can use strength/density index (SDI) defined in the following equation as the basis of determination of effectiveness.

$$SDI = (\Delta P/P)/(\Delta \rho/\rho) \quad (2)$$

where $\Delta P/P$ is the percent increase in the load carrying capacity resulting from the addition of steel shim and $\Delta \rho/\rho$ is the corresponding percent increase in specimen density. The corresponding SDI values for different steel shim contents are shown in Table IV and are graphed in Fig. 6.

Table IV. SDI Values

Specimen Designation	0M	1M	2M	4M
Density, g/cm ³	1.64	2.08	2.35	2.93
Load Carrying Capacity, Kg*	759	993	1543	2113
SDI	1	1.15	2.42	2.27

*Data for $e/D = 3.15$, $W/D = 5$. (Full bearing strength was attended.)

It seems that the optimized strengthening effectiveness based on strength/weight consideration occurred in the region that the steel shim content is between 11.91% and 22.93%. It also appears that the strengthening effectiveness has already been in a descendent tendency for the specimen with 22.93% of steel shim. Although the bearing strength for the specimen with steel shim. Although the bearing strength for the specimen with steel shim greater than 22.93% may still increase, designers should pay attention to the descent tendency of strength effectiveness.

Fig. 6 - Correlation between SDI and laminate density.

Minimum Values of e/D and W/D to Reach Full Bearing Strength

It is well known that full bearing strength for mechanically fastened joints is only attained when the ratios of e/D and W/D are above certain minimum values [4-9, 12-13]. The current study shows that laminates with steel interlayered reinforcement behave in a similar manner. Fig. 7 shows the bearing strength with e/D for the specimens with different steel shim contents. It appears that the minimum value of e/D to ensure the full bearing strength is 3.15 and is regardless to the steel shim content. Thus the addition of steel interlayer does enhance the bearing carrying capacity (see Fig. 7), but it will not affect the needed minimum value of e/D .

The value of W/D affects the stress distribution in net section more remarkably. In the present study, the minimum value of W/D to attain full bearing strength is dependent on the steel shim content. For the cases of low value of V_s , such as 0 and 6.59%, this minimum value of W/D is 3.8. While it is 5 for the cases of higher value of V_s , such as 11.91 and 22.93%. It is obvious that the addition of steel shim not only enhanced the bearing load capacity, but also increased the net tension stress across the hole section and induced the tension failure. A way to avoid this premature tension failure is to increase the value of W/D . That is the reason why the value of W/D should be larger enough to attain the full bearing strength for those specimens with higher steel shim content. So, the use of steel shim to improve joint efficiency should consider the possible increase of W/D ratio to ensure the full bearing strength to be obtainable.

Figure 7 - Correlation between bearing strength and e/D ratio (W/D=3.8).

Figure 8 - Correlation between bearing and W/D ratio (e/D=3.15).

Influence of Adding Steel Shim on Failure Mode

In general, the failure mode of mechanically bolted joints is affected by specimen geometric parameters. The major parameters are ratios of e/D and W/D . At low values of e/D the specimen will fail by shear along two planes from the end of the hole diameter in a direction of loading, the so-called shear out mode, or will fail by cleaving the plies apart which results a split parallel to the load, the so-called cleavage mode. At low values of W/D the specimen will fail in tension through the hole, and this failure is so-called tension mode. The most desirable failure mode is so-called bearing mode, which occurs when the bolt plows through the laminate. The essential condition to occur the bearing failure is that the ratios of e/D and W/D should be greater than corresponding minimum values. Because the bearing failure is not catastrophic and usually continues to withstand considerably more load, it is the most effective for the mechanical joints. The four typical failure modes are schematically drawn in Fig. 9.

Figure 9 - Schematic failure modes of mechanically bolted joint.

How does the addition of steel shim affect the failure mode? Because the steel shim will change the condition of stress concentration and provide higher local strength, therefore it should affect the failure mode in some ways. The failure modes have been listed in Table II and some critical failure appearances are shown in Fig. 10.

At low values of e/D , such as $e/D = 2$, $W/D = 3.8$, the specimens without steel shim failed in tension, while the cleavage failure occurred for the specimens with steel shim (Fig. 10 [a]). By the increase of e/D ratio, for example, $e/D \geq 3.15$, the initial failure was by bearing, and ultimate failure was by tension (we indicated this mode in bearing/tension), and this result would not be changed by the steel shim content (Fig. 10[b]). Note that the shear-out failure is not the case in the present study.

At low values of W/D ratio, such $W/D = 3.0$, $e/D = 3.15$, the specimens failed in tension in spite of the addition of steel shim (Fig. 10[c]). By the increase of W/D ratio, the failure mode was bearing/tension (Fig. 10 [d] and [e]). But when W/D ratio was large, for example, $W/D = 7.6$, the specimen was too wide to occur the tension failure and the ultimate failure was by cleavage instead of tension (Fig. 10[f]).

Two sets of specimens should be pointed out here: (1) When W/D and e/D ratios were in intermediate values, for example, $W/D = 3.8$, $e/D = 3.15$, the bearing/tension mode was the case of failure for the specimens with low steel

[a] $W/D = 3.8, e/D = 2.0$

[b] $W/D = 3.8, e/D = 6.0$

[c] $W/D = 3.0, e/D = 3.15$

[d] $W/D = 3.8, e/D = 3.15$

[e] $W/D=5.0, e/D=3.15$

[f] $W/D=7.6, e/D=3.5$

[g] $W/D=8, e/D=6$

Figure 10 - Failure appearances.

shim content ($V_s = 0$ or 6.59%). But pure tension failure occurred for the specimens with high steel shim content ($V_s = 11.91$ or 22.93%). Therefore, it seems that the addition of steel shim will induce the specimen failure in tension more or less (Fig. 10[d]). (2) When W/D and e/D ratios were all large, for example, $W/D \geq 8$, $e/D \geq 6$, only pure bearing failure occurred (Fig. 10[g]). This is the desired failure mode.

Conclusively, the failure mode is affected by the steel shim content in some cases. The proper values of W/D and e/D to ensure the full bearing strength should be inspected by the designers.

Conclusions

The joint strengthening effect of adding steel shim reinforcement in a glass cloth/epoxy laminate has been experimentally determined. From the present study the following conclusions can be made:

- (1) A linear relationship between bearing strength and volume fraction of steel shim V_s is existed for the value of V_s below 22.93%. The full bearing strength for the specimens with 6.59, 11.91 and 22.93% steel shim is 30.8, 103, 178% higher than those of specimens without steel shim, respectively. Obviously a substantial improvement in bearing strength is gained by adding the high strength and ductile steel shim.
- (2) Based on strength/density consideration, the optimized strengthening effectiveness of adding steel shim is for specimen with the value of V_s fell somewhere between 11.91 and 22.93%. The SDI value has been in a descendent tendency for the specimen with steel shim of 22.93%.
- (3) The minimum value of e/D to ensure the full bearing strength is 3.15 and this value is regardless to the steel shim content. While the minimum value of W/D to attain the full bearing strength is dependent on the steel shim content. For the cases of low value of V_s , such as 0 and 6.59%, this minimum value of W/D is 3.8, and is 5 for the cases of higher value of V_s , such as 11.91 and 22.93%.
- (4) The failure mode is affected by the addition of steel shim in some cases. At the low values of e/D , such as $e/D = 2$, $W/D = 3.8$, the specimens without steel shim failed in tension, while the cleavage failure occurred for the specimens with steel shim. By the increase of e/D ratio, for example, $e/D \geq 3.15$, the initial failure was by bearing and ultimate failure was by tension.
- (5) At the low value of W/D ratio, such as $W/D = 3.0$, $e/D = 3.15$, the specimens failed in tension in spite of the addition of steel shim. By the increase of W/D ratio, the failure mode was bearing/tension, then bearing/cleavage. When W/D and e/D ratios were all large, for example, $W/D \geq 8$, $e/D \geq 6$, only pure bearing failure occurred.
- (6) It seems that the addition of steel shim will induce the specimen failure in tension more or less.

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